

CLIMATE CHANGE - CAUSES, CONSEQUENCES AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: In this article there is information about why climate change is happening and what can happen because of this problem. Also what can we do for overcoming this issue.

Key words: climate change, CO₂, methane, fossil fuels, sea levels, underwater cities, human activities, warmer periods, greenhouse gases.

In today's world climate change is one of the biggest issues around the planet. Almost all the countries are facing this problem in some cases of their. Firstly, what is climate change? It is a problem that leads to warmer periods.

What can cause to this issue? Most climatologists and experts point out that human activities are the biggest part of climate change. According to statistics 95% of this problem is caused by people in the world. One of them is using too much CO₂, because around the world there are lots of factories and manufactories which use CO₂ to produce products. They burn fossil fuels like oil, coal, gas during producing process which harms the air and causes this phenomenon problem. Additional information is usage of CO₂ increased drastically from 1950. At the same time, population of the world has doubled since three-four decades that grows the need for foods. In that case people are eating more animal products, especially their meat which is a way of producing harmful element methane.

When these useless gases are produced by human activities, they release into the air and heat the planet which is a process of climate change. As a result of that

UN has identified average temperature is 1 degree harder than 1800 and speed of it is too fast which can increase to 1.5 degree, even 2 degree by 2100.

Consequences of this change can impact on oceans, weather, food health. Sea levels become rising and sea water expands that can effect the way people live and build their houses. Meaning, in some countries residents are constructing their house on the water that are called floating cities. However, when it's windy houses crack and owners need to repair them again. Also people have been interviewed about their living they have said this type of houses have been easy to contact with others except for its downside. When it comes to weather there are storms, floods, heavy snow fall droughts which can be dangerous for people's life and they may be out their houses. Result in they need to reconstruct their houses to live. For example in some countries it happens and their population's life comes to an edge. These weather issues can also has an affect to food. To illustrate, if there is drought, water diminishes and farmers, gardeners may not have opportunities to water crops and whole country's agriculture may be effected, it can lead to famine as well. Health is also involved in this issue, as temperature rises, people can have problems related to their health, such as facing blood pressure, problem in cardiovascular system, astma, heart disease and so on.

On the other hand, there are possible actions that we can take to overcome this difficulty. Before, people should be informed about the biggest problem, particularly why it is happening, how it can impact on us by giving speeches and making videos, films on social media. Next step can be reduction of using carbon dioxide and using products of animals. If they know about their results, they may change their lifestyle.